

MUSICOLOGY

ИЗ ИСТОРИИ КАМЕРНОГО ОРКЕСТРА ЛЕНИНАКАНА

Хачатрян Д.К.

*Доцент фортепианного отделения, Гюмрийский филиал Ереванской государственной консерватории имени Комитаса
Армения, г.Гюмри*

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE LENINAKAN CHAMBER ORCHESTRA

Khachatryan D.

*Docent of the Piano Department,
Komitas State Conservatory of Yerevan Gyumri branch
Armenia, Gyumri*

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается история формирования и деятельности камерных оркестров Ленинакана с 1960-х годов до конца 1970-х. Представлены коллективы под руководством Сергея Мацоояна, Татула Егиазаряна и Григора Даниеляна, их концертные программы, гастроли и художественные инициативы. Особое внимание уделяется успехам государственного камерного оркестра, которым в 1977–1979 гг. руководил Григор Даниелян, его знаменательным концертам, поездкам, а также ряду премьер, состоявшихся в музыкальной жизни Армении, включая первое исполнение мистерия-сонаты Бибера. Отмечается роль культурной среды Ленинакана в развитии камерного искусства и представляется широкая панорама музыкальной жизни данного периода на основе архивных материалов прессы и интервью.

Abstract

The article examines the history of the formation and activity of Leninakan's chamber orchestras from the 1960s to the late 1970s. It presents the ensembles led by Sergey Matsoyan, Tatul Yeghiazaryan, and Grigor Danielyan, their concert programs, tours, and artistic initiatives. Special attention is given to the achievements of the state chamber orchestra conducted by Grigor Danielyan between 1977 and 1979, its notable concerts, tours, as well as a number of premieres in Armenia's musical life—including the first performance of Biber's *Mystery Sonata*. The study highlights the role of Leninakan's cultural environment in the development of chamber music and offers a comprehensive overview of the city's musical life during that period, based on archival press materials and interviews.

Ключевые слова: Камерный оркестр Ленинакана, Григор Даниелян, Сергей Мацоян, камерная музыка в Армении, концерты.

Keywords: Leninakan Chamber Orchestra, Grigor Danielyan, Sergey Matsoyan, Chamber Music in Armenia, Concerts.

In the 1960s, two chamber orchestras operated in Leninakan. The first was conducted by Sergey Matsoyan. Sergey Matsoyan was born and spent his childhood and adolescence in Leninakan. He studied at the Kara-Murza Music College and later received his higher education at the Kyiv State Tchaikovsky Conservatory, completing postgraduate studies at the same institution. Afterward, he began working at the Odesa Philharmonic, rising from assistant conductor of the symphony orchestra to its principal conductor.

In 1967, he returned to Leninakan, initially serving as director of the Kara-Murza Music College and later as head of the Music Department at the M. Nalbandyan Pedagogical Institute. Alongside his pedagogical work, he formed a state chamber ensemble, which operated for several years but was later dissolved due to failure to meet performance quotas. Subsequently, Tatul Yeghiazaryan returned from the Baltic region to Leninakan and founded a 16-member chamber orchestra. The ensemble staged Artemi Ayvazyan's musical *"The Dentist from the East."* Concert tickets have been preserved that attest to Yeghiazaryan's active performance activities. Their repertoire included

works by Haydn, Mozart, Vivaldi, Shostakovich, Komitas, and other prominent composers. Unfortunately, the orchestra operated for only two years and was disbanded due to the lack of a rehearsal space (according to an interview with musician Khachik Chalikyan, who performed in these ensembles).

Later, between 1977 and 1979, a chamber orchestra was once again established in Leninakan, this time under the direction of Grigor Danielyan (known as Daniel Musician). In an interview, he recalled those years with great affection:

"The orchestra I conducted had originally been founded by Sergey Matsoyan. I came in after Matsoyan left for Odesa," said G. Danielyan.

Everything began when he participated in — and won — the competition announced for the vacant position of opera-symphonic conductor. A week later, Edgar Hovhannisyan, who at the time was the artistic director of the Philharmonic, called him and said that there were already enough conductors at the opera. *"It would be better for you to go to Leninakan,"* he told him, explaining that Karen Demirchyan was concerned

that, after Sergey Matsoyan and T. Yeghiazaryan, the chamber orchestra in Leninakan needed a conductor. Thus, Grigor Danielyan was assigned to Leninakan.

“After Sergey Matsoyan, people would say: ‘Leninakan is the second city—how can its orchestra remain without a conductor? It was second, but not secondary,’” says G. Danielyan.

Edgar Hovhannisyanyan later told him, “*I am your godfather—as a conductor.*” This was how Danielyan arrived in Leninakan, though even before that he had been teaching at the Kara-Murza Music College. Danielyan prepared a program with the orchestra, which then had to be assessed by an artistic council. That council included prominent musicologists Robert Atayan and Margarit Harutyunyan.

The chamber orchestra of Leninakan appeared before the music lovers of the capital. For many, this was the first encounter with the only ensemble representing the chamber genre of our republic’s second city. And it should be noted that this encounter left a pleasant impression. Several artists present at the concert shared their thoughts about the evening.

Robert Atayan (musicologist): “*The very fact of the existence of the Leninakan Chamber Orchestra is already a welcome phenomenon in our cultural life. A group of enthusiastic young musicians has undertaken a very commendable mission. Under the direction of the talented musicologist and gifted conductor G. Danielyan, they have prepared, with such a small ensemble, a tastefully selected repertoire, which this evening produced a very gratifying impression. We hope and believe that the ensemble will yet speak with its full voice, bringing aesthetic pleasure to audiences many times over.*”

Gerondi Talalyan (cellist, Honored Artist of the Armenian SSR, professor) – “*The Chamber Orchestra of Leninakan is an ensemble endowed with great potential. Today we were once again convinced of this.*”

(“Yerevan Erekoian,” 10.03.1978)

“*We gave a concert at Tartu’s European-standard concert hall together with S. Navasardyan and my late wife, Ruzanna Hovsepian. That was the orchestra’s first concert tour,*” recalls G. Danielyan.

There was still plenty of time before the start of the intercity Friendship Evening–Festival, yet the hall was already packed with visitors.

In addition to the nearly 120 delegates who had arrived from Leninakan, many residents of Tartu—primarily representatives of the youth of the sister city—had gathered to attend the event.

It is eight o’clock in the evening. The First Secretary of the Tartu City Party Committee, Juhanes Lott, announces the opening of the Friendship Evening.

Then, together with the Chairman of the City Executive Committee, Comrade Ilpi, he presents Certificates of Commendation from the Tartu City Party Committee and the City Executive Committee to the following: the Department of Culture of the Leninakan City Executive Committee, the Sevyan Cultural Palace’s Song and Dance Ensemble, the “Aragats” Vocal-Instrumental Ensemble of the Builders’ Cultural Palace,

the State Chamber Ensemble, Honored Artist of the Armenian SSR A. Shaboyan, H. Sukiasyan, Honored Painter of the Armenian SSR Kh. Vardparonyan, V. Ohanjanyan, and G. Danielyan. (“Banvor,” 02.11.1978)

“*We also performed with our pride and my close friend, the brilliant pianist Alexei Lyubimov,*” the maestro recalls again.

The Leninakan branch of Arkhimconcert opened its 1978–1979 concert season. The city’s State Chamber Orchestra, conducted by G. Danielyan, appeared in concert. Performing as soloist was pianist Alexei Lyubimov—soloist of the Moscow Philharmonic and laureate of international competitions.

Program:

- J. Haydn – Concerto for Piano and Orchestra (D major)

- W. A. Mozart – Concerto for Piano and Orchestra (F major)

- A. Vivaldi – *Madrigalesco*

- P. I. Tchaikovsky – Waltz

- Ryayets – Concerto for Violin and Orchestra, soloist: G. Danielyan

- A. Shishyan – Arrangements of Armenian folk songs: *Materi* and *Pakhari*

- Provo – Concerto

- Y. Balyan – Scherzo

- A. Vivaldi – Concerto for Violin and Organ with Orchestra, organ: A. Lyubimov (“Banvor,” 22.09.1978)

“*I also performed with Tigran Adamyanyan, who was the director of the Kara-Murza College and a wonderful cellist,*” says G. Danielyan.

The concert took place in Leninakan in 1978 and consisted of two parts:

First Part:

- A. Vivaldi – Cello Concerto (G major)

- A. Vivaldi – *Largo*

- A. Corelli – Trio Sonata

- G. Danielyan – *Song of Friendship Soloist: Tigran Adamyanyan (cello)*

Second Part:

- J. S. Bach – Piano Concerto No. 5

- A. Vivaldi – Concerto for Flute, Oboe, and Bassoon

- Stradella – Aria

- J. S. Bach – Fugue No. 3 from *The Art of Fugue*

- M. Yekmalyan – Excerpt from the *Patarag* (Liturgy)

- A. Shishyan – *At the Tomb of the Unknown Soldier*, arranged by G. Danielyan

Soloist: Diploma-holder of the 3rd Transcaucasian Competition Ruzanna Hovsepian.

“*I performed as soloist, playing A. Corelli. I also played the violin concerto by the contemporary Estonian composer J. Andres, during which I both performed and conducted the orchestra—this was in Estonia itself,*” recounts G. Danielyan.

“*We also gave concerts in various regions of Armenia,*” adds the maestro.

The State Chamber Orchestra of Leninakan has performed numerous times in Kirovakan, Artik, and other regions and cities of the republic, consistently earning high praise from music lovers. “Recently the orchestra performed for the music enthusiasts of Kajaran and Kapan. For the first time, accompanied by the organ (organist: laureate of the Transcaucasian Competition R. Hovsepyan), the Chamber Orchestra presented Corelli’s *Trio Sonata*. The organist then performed Bach’s *Fifth Concerto*. The horn solo in Stradella’s *Sacred Aria* was played by Vachagan Sargsyan.

The orchestra’s program also included A. Shishyan’s *At the Tomb of the Unknown Soldier*, the *Three Pieces* by Komitas–Aslamazyan, Vivaldi’s *Concerto*, Schubert’s *Barcarolle*, and other works. Among the soloists were P. Ughurlian (violin), G. Danielyan (viola), E. Khachatryan (bassoon), M. Petrosyan (cello), and others.”

(“Banvor,” 07.04.1978)

“Our orchestra had a rather interesting composition, and this had its advantages,” says G. Danielyan. “I myself made several arrangements for the ensemble—for example, Bach’s fugues. I also composed original works for the orchestra.”

“In the Chamber Orchestra,” continues G. Danielyan, “we had fourteen performers. The balance between the string and wind sections was somewhat uneven. I worked to select concert repertoire in such a way that this ‘shortage,’ so to speak, would turn into an advantage for our chamber ensemble.”

“A personal concert was held for composer Azat Shishyan,” says G. Danielyan. The concert took place on October 27, 1977, in Leninakan, again in two parts:

Artistic Director and Conductor: G. Danielyan

Soloists: Ruzanna Hovsepyan (piano), T. Adamyan (cello), Perch Ughurlian (violin), Rafik Asatryan (vocal). The concert was dedicated to the 60th anniversary of the Great October Socialist Revolution. (“Banvor,” 03.03.1978)

Danielyan also organized lecture-concerts with the orchestra, marking the 400th anniversary of Frescobaldi and the 300th anniversary of Vivaldi.

Lecture-Concert

On the occasion of the 60th anniversary of the Great October Socialist Revolution, a lecture-concert was organized at the House of Art Workers.

The lecture was delivered by G. Danielyan, Artistic Director of the Leninakan State Chamber Orchestra. Speaking about chamber music, he focused in particular on the life and works of the Italian violinist and composer Arcangelo Corelli.

Following the lecture, sonatas by Corelli were performed by:

the orchestra’s conductor and violinist G. Danielyan; violinists H. Mafyan and P. Ughurlian; cellist M. Petrosyan; pianist R. Hovsepyan; and cellist A. Simonyan.

In the concert section, the *Duo* for two violins by French composer Pleyel was also performed by G. Danielyan and H. Mafyan. The lecture-concert was instructive and took place in a warm and engaging atmosphere. (“Banvor,” 07.11.1977)

A musical evening dedicated to the great Italian violinist and composer Antonio Vivaldi was held at the House of Art Workers. G. Danielyan delivered a lecture on Vivaldi’s life and artistic path, after which the concert section began. Performed were the second and third movements of Vivaldi’s *Concerto in G minor* for flute, as well as the *Concerto in A minor* for violin.

The soloists were G. Danielyan (viola), P. Ughurlian (first violin), V. Terzibashyan (second violin), and M. Badikyan (flute). The concert also featured A. Simonyan (cello) and R. Hovsepyan (piano).

Many music lovers attended the lecture-concert, expressing their satisfaction with this remarkable event and congratulating the performers.

(“Banvor,” 03.02.1978)

The same program, with slight modifications, was later repeated at the Pedagogical College.

When asked why the ensemble eventually ceased its activity, the composer replied:

“Once Mansuryan came to Leninakan and told the director of the Philharmonic’s Leninakan branch, Jupiter Sargsyan: ‘Keep an eye on G. Danielyan—David Khanjyan, the chief conductor of the Armenian Philharmonic, wants to take him from Leninakan.’ Later, David Khanjyan asked me to come to Yerevan as his assistant conductor. And since I wanted to expand my professional activity, I left for Yerevan,” Danielyan explained.

During its existence, the ensemble premiered several works in Armenia. “With this orchestra, I performed in Armenia for the first time Heinrich Ignaz Franz von Biber’s *Mystery Sonata* for violin,” he recalled.

The maestro notes that working with the musicians of Leninakan came naturally to him, though there were occasional “enharmonic misunderstandings”—for instance, “I would say *d-sharp*, and they understood *e-flat*.”

Thus, from 1977 to 1979, the State Chamber Orchestra operated in Leninakan under the direction of Grigor Danielyan. In the interview, he highlighted the concert in Tartu as a particularly important milestone—the ensemble’s first international concert tour. The Chamber Orchestra performed Corelli’s *Trio Sonata* for the first time with organ accompaniment.

Concerts were also held marking the 400th anniversary of Frescobaldi and the 300th anniversary of Vivaldi. Among the orchestra’s notable performances, special attention should be given to the concert featuring the brilliant pianist Alexei Lyubimov, who performed Haydn’s *Concerto in D major* and Mozart’s *Concerto in F major* with the ensemble.

The orchestra also toured Estonia, where Grigor Danielyan appeared as soloist, performing Corelli’s works as well as the violin concerto by contemporary Estonian composer Jaan Rääts—leading the orchestra while also playing the solo part.

In Leninakan, one of the major artistic achievements of this ensemble was the Armenian premiere of Heinrich Ignaz Franz von Biber’s *Mystery Sonata* for violin.

References

1. "Banvor" Daily Newspaper, 1970s.
2. Interview with conductor, violinist, musicologist, public figure, composer, Honored Artist of Armenia, and recipient of the Golden Medal of the Ministry of Culture of Armenia, Grigor Danielyan (Daniel the Musician). 25.11.2025, Gyumri